

Turn-taking and Cooperation Principles on “*Catatan Demokrasi Kita*” and Its Implications in Indonesian Language Learning

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Abstract

Turn-taking is the part of conversation principles that can be used as a reference in speaking. The use of the conversion principle contains unique characteristics and styles of communication for each speaker. A talk show is an open stage for politicians to show their ability to speak and implement the speech strategy. However, the context of the conversion tends to change the conditions of the speech strategy. This research is qualitative. The data was collected by using the documentation method. The data sources were obtained from the conversations during the Talk Show “*Catatan Demokrasi Kita*” on the TV One 'channel. This study applied a formal method to present the result of the conversation data analysis in the classification table of the politician’s speech strategy. The informal method was used to express the speech that classified into how to take over the turn-taking and to apply the corporation principle. This research is also implied to Indonesian learning, especially speaking skills.

1. Introduction

A language is a communication tool in the form of a sound symbol system used by speakers to express cultural and social values and norms in a language process (Bonvillain, 2019). A language that is the expression of thoughts and feelings is packaged in a speech. The speech that takes place

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has a goal to be achieved. Speech events occur in forms of social interaction in society. Such as speeches, preaching, dialogues, discussions, seminars, workshops, symposia, workshops, and other forms of social interaction. Speech events can also occur in speech titles. The said event is a public activity that involves politicians or someone who is invited to the event. The talk show addresses the topics prepared by the moderator. Such as the latest political issues that are being discussed by the community or the form of public policy that has just been decided.

Hornby (1974) states that a talk show or speech title is a speaking activity that intends to provide information in a discussion, debate, or another form of speaking activity. This activity is guided by a moderator who plays the role of directing, giving a turn to speak, and leading the speaking activity to completion. The guide in his role is to provide questions to the speakers and divide the number of turns to speak to the speech act participants. Speech titles allow politicians to convey views on a political event. Politicians' speech also serves a purpose. The speech objectives that the speakers want to achieve, in this case the politicians, depending on their position and role in the speech. For example, to maintain party electability, maintain self-existence, appear to be in favor of the people, or other objectives that underlie the narrative to take place and the opportunity to speak it gets.

All speech events, as stated, have a purpose following the background of a speech. According to Shaykhislamov & Makhmudov (2020), the purpose of speech is what the speaker wants to achieve by acting on speaking. This component is the background of the speech because all speeches have a purpose. Therefore, speakers need to master how to speak properly so that all utterances to be conveyed to speakers in speech acts are well received.

Fishman & Anderson (1971) state a "sociolinguistic study of who speaks what language to whom and when." Sociolinguistics field deals with the study of language and power, language solidarity, when and in what situations the community and culture use that language, and who are the speakers and speakers in language communication (Cf. Poole, 2020). The principle of conversation is the knowledge of speakers and speakers, in this case, the politicians, and their ability to manage speech. It is important to pay attention to managing the ability to speak. After getting a turn to speak, of course, maximizing the principle of cooperation so that on this occasion, it can be an opportunity, not a threat to someone in a conversation because how the quality of the speech and the content of the speech also needs to be considered.

Politicians are public figures whose speaking style and quality are observed by the public. In addition, some politicians have become people's representatives, so it is important to reflect the polite personality they want. Speech events can be carried out by understanding the principles of conversation and paying attention to when it is the turn to speak (Winch, 2020). Turn to speak is an important value because, for a speaker who does not understand when it is his turn to speak, he will take over the turn at will. Such speech events will provide an uncomfortable atmosphere for the speaker. A speaker who feels he always loses the opportunity to speak if the speech occurs in an unbalanced proportion creates negative perceptions and judgments of the other person.

The variety of speech that appears can be caused by the interesting topic of conversation and also because of efforts to maintain one's quality in front of the public (Tan et al., 2021). This is due to the importance of continuing the conversation on the topics discussed. Politicians can argue with each other, support arguments, and show their quality in understanding the topics discussed. In implementing such a speech event, every speaker who changes roles to become one must have a narrative strategy that he uses. Observation of the sequential strategies used by politicians is an important thing to observe and make into a study.

This research focuses on politicians' conversations on speech titles and tries to observe the turn of speech changes and the use of conversation principles. Using the method of taking over speech and the principle of cooperation between politicians when speaking is important to study because politicians are public figures whose activities are closely related to society. In speech titles, of course, these speeches are broadcast for the public to watch, their style can also be imitated. This study seeks

to find turn-taking and the application of the principles of cooperation used by politicians in dialogue on the talk show "Notes on Our Democracy" on TV One and implies the results of research on Indonesian language learning, especially speaking skills in the competence of discussion or debate.

Politicians have the characteristics and abilities to portray themselves as speakers and change roles as speech partners (Grossman & Helpman, 2021). This study uses speech strategies to describe successive ability in speech events. The speech strategy adopted by a speaker depends on his knowledge of managing a speech event. Politicians have an understanding of the social background, insight into language culture, and emotional management so that the objectives of the conversation are achieved properly (Latupeirissa et al., 2018, 2019; Laksana, 2021). Furthermore, this study implies the politician's speech strategy in the subject matter of Indonesian language lectures, especially discussion or debate skills.

2. Materials and Methods

Theoretical Review

Fishman (2020) states a sociolinguistic study of who speaks what language to whom and when. Sociolinguistics field deals with the study of language and power, language solidarity, when and in what situations the community and culture use that language, and who the speakers and speakers of language communication are. Speech transfer is a change of speaking roles performed by speakers and speech partners. The conversation will change the role of the speaker to become a speech partner or speech opponent and vice versa. In connection with this, there is a research journal Ruth, E. Corp et al. (2018) "Early Preparation During Turn-Taking: Listeners Use Content Predictions to Determine what to say but not when to say it." His research discusses an experiment on speakers and interlocutors in a communication event related to the preparation to take over the turn of speaking in response to a content being spoken. Sacks et al. (1978) state that the formulation of the basic rules of speech transference is as follows. (1) If the speech change has been determined by appointing the next speaker, then the appointed participant has the right to speak. (2) If the speech change is not determined, the conversation participants will decide who will speak next after the previous speaker has allowed the next participant. (3) If the speech change is not determined in advance, and other participants do not take the initiative to become a speaker, the previous speaker can continue and use the opportunity to speak.

Another opinion was also expressed by Edmonson et al. (1981). According to Edmonson et al. (1981: 39), there are rules for changing speech. These rules can be seen in the following details. (1) If I give it my turn, you must take it. (2) If I show readiness to give my turn to speak, you must speak. (3) If you can't, I will continue. Burns et al. (2003) suggest that based on their presentation, communication events involve two or more people. Changing speaking roles between speakers and speech partners who exchange positions is not done randomly because turn-taking norms regulate it. Shifting patterns are norms or rules that determine conventionally who speaks, when, and for how long. Speakers who do not understand the rotation pattern will dominate the conversation and will not allow the conversation partner to speak. On the other hand, speakers who do not take advantage of the opportunity to speak will cause their speech to stop suddenly. Therefore, the proportion and change of roles of speakers and speech partners must be mastered through the norm of a rotating pattern.

Conversations can be carried out by selecting listeners using the closest speech pair. Another conversational analysis theory by Levinson (1983: 296) is about rotational patterns. The discussion about the shifting pattern is a fundamental organization of a conversation that is applied to obtain a harmonious interaction. Taking turns in a conversation can be done in some ways. The means include (1)

obtaining, (2) stealing, (3) seizing, (4) substituting, (5) creating, and (6) continuing. The following further explains these methods (Rani et al., 2004: 215).

Pragmatics is a field of science that studies how an utterance is meaningful in a particular context (Gunasari et al., 2020). Moreover, pragmatics is a science that studies the use of language. Taguchi (2019) states that pragmatics is closely related to language use, namely how language is used by its speakers in actual situations and interactions. Based on the above opinion, it can be concluded that pragmatics is a field of linguistics that studies how language is meaningful in a particular speech situation. The involvement of the context in this field of science can be the basis for determining how an utterance has meaning and meaning following what is expected by the speaker.

Research design

In general, this study aims to determine the use of how to take turns to speak and the application of the principles of conversation in a speech title. This research is qualitative. The strategy used in this research is a case study. A case study, according to Radez et al. (2021), is a research strategy that involves researchers investigating a program, event, activity, process, or group of individuals. Presentation of data with a formal method, namely the formulation using signs or symbols, while the informal method is the formulation using detailed words, including the use of technical terminology.

Sample

The subjects in this research were politicians in the Talk Show "Notes on Our Democracy" on TV One. There are nine impressions in 60 minutes duration for each broadcast. The basis for selecting the research sample was only the speech of the politician who appeared in the speech title. It is done because the language of politicians is a language that reflects public figures who become role models.

Instruments and Procedures

This research will describe the speech strategies used by politicians in a speech title. The instrument used in this study as a means of downloading impressions that would be documented and transcribing impression data which would then be applied to the coding sheet technique.

3. Results and Discussions

Conversation Speech (ATP)

Speech transfer is a change of speaking roles in a conversation or speech title. Changing the role of speaking can be done with the experts' rules. Like Edmonson (1981: 39) and Rani et al. (2004: 215), there are rules for changing speech.

The following is an explanation of the analytical data found in the domain of politicians' changing turn of speech in the talk show "Notes on Our Democracy" on TV One.

Data 1 Field Notes 1 / ATP Obtained:

MC: I went straight to Bang Daniel,...

Daniel: I think the evidence for,

If I turn to speak, you must take it (Edmonson, 1981). In the above speech, it can be seen that the MC members have the opportunity to speak, and Dahnil takes turns speaking by obtaining. He got the opportunity to speak, which was given directly by the moderator to him.

Data 2 Field Note 2 / ATP Stole:

MC: It was similar to what happened to Irma's mother, right?

P1: Not only in my electoral district, in all electoral districts...

P2: So three external factors came out ... (continued)

P2, in the conversation above, did speech transfer by stealing because in a situation when the moderator allowed P1 to speak, suddenly P2 took his turn to speak. The first speaker (P1) did not expect that the speech partner would take turns speaking (Rani et al., 2004). Therefore, P1's speech stopped and immediately moved to P2. The speech was said to have been stolen because after P2 took over, P1 no longer had the opportunity to speak.

Data 3 Field Note 3 / ATP Grab:

Tejo: Oh yeah, right. Why are you afraid this is deploying ASN?

M: The facts in the field are like that. Starting from the head of the service, then the sub-the district head, to RT / RW

MC: Is it all Bang Miing's experience?

M: O... We don't have this evidence.

I: In us, the Primordial is still thick (continued).

M: Mas Tejo, isn't it a little, Madam Irma?

I took over the turn to speak by grabbing because M was talking to Tejo, then I took his turn to speak because M had not finished speaking, so M took back the next opportunity to speak after I spoke. Seizing is a speech transition that occurs when the previous speaker (M) is talking and wants to continue the conversation (Rani et al., 2004).

Data 4 Field Notes 4 / ATP Creates:

MC: Well, what was interesting was the word attack of money that was hard to fight in the field of ce popong ... it proved five periods, right?

Popong: please sentence now?

Tejo: Yes, the current sentence (teasing) ...

Prie: Did you pop out a lot of money at that time?

Popong: No, I don't spend much money... Can I ask why? If ... someone wants to be a candidate, there are two capitals. The first is financial capital...

Popong's speech created a speaking opportunity for himself. This was evident from the questions raised by the MC, which were not yet concrete, then added by Prie so that only the full speaking opportunity was given to Popong to answer all questions from the MC and Prie as his talking partners. Creating is a way of taking a speaking turn by bringing up new speeches that are different but still have something to do with previous speeches (Rani et al. 2004). Popong's first speech creates a new one that is expressed by Prie, so that Popong gets the opportunity to talk again to answer Prie's questions firmly in the conversation.

Data 5 Field Notes 5 / ATP Continued:

Continuing is a way of taking over the next speaking turn because the speech partner does not take advantage of the opportunity to speak (Sack et al., 1974). Example :

*Turn-taking and Cooperation Principles on "Catatan Demokrasi Kita"
and Its Implications in Indonesian Language Learning
(I Wayan Ardi Sumarta; I Wayan Simpen; I Ketut Darma Laksana; Ketut Artawa)*

P1: It's really cold today, right ..?

P2: (silent) is replying to a Whatsapp message

P1: You're not cold?

P2: It's pretty cold.

In the speech in the speech title, there is no data to continue. This happens because every politician, in this case, certainly has good readiness and concentration in speech so that the opportunity to speak will be used as best as possible by them. What happens in politicians' speech titles is fighting over the opportunity to speak.

Data 6 Field Note 6 / ATP Replaces:

Miftah Sabri: Mas Bambang, Mas Bambang Mas Deni suggests Satria choose to compete. I also think maybe the teacher's playing post for Pak Feri. He already understands that the witnesses saw, heard, knew, and what his name was brought there, and in my opinion, Pak Feri has a bit different opinion.

Moderator: Will it not be anti-climax?

Miftah Sabri: No, I mean this, you know... (continued).

The transition of speech in the above conversation is done by changing. Miftah changed her speech because what was conveyed to the MC had different perceptions from what she meant, so Miftah looked for other words to explain the same meaning in the speech. Changing is a transition because the speech partner cannot understand speech (Rani et al., 2004).

Principles of Cooperation

This principle regulates how a conversation goal is achieved so that the speaker and speaker contribute actively to each other to make the conversation clear and easy to understand and in accordance with the proportions. Grice (1975) states that the principle of cooperation is poured into four maxims, namely the maxim of quantity, the maxim of quality, the maxim of relevance, and the maxim of manner.

Data 1 Field Notes 1 / PK Maximum Quality

Moderator: and they run under the law?

Johnny Plate: in the law and who is it produced by, all the factions that are the supporters of these two pairs of candidates in the DPR with the government if we want to return to debate the general election law or debate the trial of constitutional results, we are not finished Now is the time, we believe in constitutional justices.

The speech delivered by Plate contains a maxim of quality because, in this speech, the speaker tries to convey the meaning of his speech based on existing facts and evidence that supports his speech (Grice, 1975). The fact is that laws are drafted by the government and members of the DPR who are elected from the party of 2 pairs of presidential candidates.

Data 2 Field Notes 2 / PK Maximum Quantity:

Lukman Edy: the second measure is, for example, voter participation.

Moderator: okay.

Lukman Edy: In the past, 75% now 81% of voter participation is also part of the KPU's perspective. This is stated as our success in improving the quality of elections.

Edy's speech adheres to the maxim of quantity. He conveyed the data on the increase in the number of voters, which rose from 75% to 81%. This speech does not tend to his party or political opponents because this is the success of the election organizer, namely the KPU. Edy provides information not based on assumptions but based on data (Grice, 1975).

Data 3 Field Notes 3 / PK Maxim Manner:

Popong: now there is one more kind from ce popong right ... there are people who actually should be elected because something is happening in their party, they are disadvantaged by their party, for example, a small example, P3 Ce Popong has a friend from P3

Miing : Miss Reni?

Popong : His name is Reni, smart, diligent, Ce Popong, sure that he will be re-elected, apparently not a victim of his party...

Popong speech adheres to the maxims of method because, in the speech, Popong delivers a description of the person in question in a specific way so that the accuracy of the speech partner proves the success of the goal of the speech in responding to the figure in question. Maksi Cara is a maxim that expects the speaker to speak, unambiguously, and not too much (Grice, 1975).

Data 4 Field Notes 4 / PK Maximum Relevance:

Moderator: at the end of the trial of the Constitutional Court, the viewers of the Chief Justice of the Constitutional Court, Anwar Usman, stated that what were the things that were revealed in the trial would be used as a basis for uncovering the truth and also justice so trust the Constitutional Court of the results Bang Ahmad Basarah, your notes at the trial yesterday!

Ahmad Basarah: Yes, as a nation, we have agreed that since the beginning of Indonesia's independence, we adhere to the principles of democracy based on law, the dynamics of building a nation on the basis of democracy and the dialectic of law, up to this stage of the Reformation Era. The maxim of relevance is related to the establishment of cooperation between speakers and speech partners, each of which makes a contribution that is relevant or following what is being said (Grice, 1975). In this data, Basarah has adhered to the principle of cooperation to the maxim of relevance. Basarah's speech has relevance to what was conveyed by previous speakers who talked about the Constitutional Court's decision, which was based on all data in the trial and the result of the ongoing democratic process.

Implications to Language Learning

The Formal Speaking course is a compulsory subject for the continuation of the Basics of Speaking course that needs to be studied and mastered by students as prospective teachers and researchers in Indonesian Language and Literature. This course provides various theories and practices so that students know, understand, and can practice various speaking skills in formal/official scientific and non-scientific forums, learning activities, and everyday life. Formal

*Turn-taking and Cooperation Principles on "Catatan Demokrasi Kita"
and Its Implications in Indonesian Language Learning
(I Wayan Ardi Sumarta; I Wayan Simpen; I Ketut Darma Laksana; Ketut Artawa)*

Speaking courses are a compulsory subject for 3rd-semester students weighing three credits. This course discusses and practices (1) MCs, (2) Types of Speeches, (3) Types of Discussions, (4) Interviews, and (5) Debates. Research on speech strategies can support speaking theories to carry out debate practice. Lecturers can make the results of the research as a reference for speaking theory and strategies in speaking so that students can become good speakers during discussions or debates. The criterion for student learning completeness is when he can carry out a discussion or debate and teach it with each person's characteristics and speaking styles.

4. Conclusion

Formal speaking learning requires theory, practice, and examples of speech that students in the learning process can duplicate. To find learners' characteristics and uniqueness and speaking style, it is necessary to provide a description of the speaker's character. How to take turns speaking is a skill that becomes the basis for discussion switching so that it can dominate and the principle of cooperation in conversation discussions makes all participants feel grateful for our existence in the discussion. With this description, students will be able to find their respective characteristics and be ready to carry out discussions or debates, and as prospective teachers, they must also be ready to teach their students later.

Limitations and The Future Study

Previous and related research only talk about each element built in this study. Previous research only discusses turn shifts in speaking, and other studies also discuss applying the principle of cooperation. This research tries to accommodate successive shifts and the application of the principle of cooperation so that it can become a speech strategy in discussions or debates. The next researcher is suggested to combine other conversational principles, such as the principle of politeness.

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